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Everyone Has the Right to Their Share: A Gendered Reading of Olive Production and Distribution in South Morocco

by Lucille FLORENZA

Abstract: The olive harvest season creates a temporality and a landscape that shape social and economic relations. This moment of collective effervescence surrounding an emblematic agricultural activity of the Mediterranean area offers an interesting perspective for thinking about the negotiation of social relations in this region. In the Sous region of Morocco, as elsewhere, the gendered division of agricultural work and the unequal distribution of the resources and of the fruits of the production are at the heart of the construction of gender dynamics. Following the path of the olives harvested in the village of Aoulouz, this article sheds light on these social constructions. The fruits are first cultivated by the owners of the trees, harvested by the hands of family members or employees, then transported, shared, pressed, and sold by others, who are more or less visible in the process. This article is the result of an investigation which took place in various olive groves and in the house of an olive-cultivating family during the winter of 2019. Specifically, an ethnography of the different protagonists and scenes of the harvest provides insights into the social roles and assignments which set the stage for an unequal distribution of the fruits of the harvest. At the core of these disparities, gender dynamics play an important role in the distribution of tasks and benefits of the harvest, from the fields to domestic spaces. By taking a particular interest in a little-explored sector and by stepping inside olive producers' homes, this article provides keys to understanding the gender-based unequal social constructions and the transformations at work in the rural areas of Morocco.

Keywords: Rural Morocco; olive growing; harvest; seasonal agricultural work; access to resources and land; women; gender.

In Provence, a region of Southern France, there is a saying that goes like this: “It takes a madman in the tree and a kind maiden underneath it to harvest its olives.”¹ The ethnographic research on which this article is based focuses on the importance of the question of gender as a “useful category of analysis” (Scott, 1988) in order to understand this gendered distribution. The moment of collective excitement around the emblematic Mediterranean agricultural activity that is the harvest of the olives offers an interesting perspective to apprehend the negotiation of social relations in that region. During my fieldwork in rural Morocco – as it is also the case elsewhere – I was able to observe the gendered division of the agricultural labour and the unequal distribution of the resources and benefits of the production, which are at the centre of the construction of gender dynamics. For under the trees, in the mills or in the homes “gender makes the sex, and not the opposite [by] over-determining the biological differentiation” (Mathieu, 2004, 63). In economic systems in which an individual’s contribution determines their right to their share of the resources, “the systematic under-evaluation of the women’s [contribution] ... reinforces their deprivation” (Agarwal, 1994, 91). Through the experience of a season of olive harvesting, this article provides an analysis of the construction of these gender inequalities and presents elements that enable us to grasp the ongoing transformations in rural Morocco.

Near Taroudant, in Morocco’s Souss region, the life of the Aoulouz villagers is rhythmmed by the rustling sound of the vareo² and by the squeaking noise of the olive press during the entire harvest. From the end of November to mid-January the village’s agricultural, economic and social activity revolves around the olive, which needs to be picked, transported to the mills and pressed before the oil is sold. The men and women of the village are all involved in these activities, to varying degrees, and agricultural labourers from the region come here to find work. The Aoulouz plain, where one of the biggest dams of the region is located, stretches from the Anti-Atlas area in the South, to the Mount Atlas in the North and the Siroua mountainous plateaus eastwards. Despite being at the junction of the trunk roads that connect Agadir with Ouarzazate and with Marrakech *via* the Atlas Mountains, the Aoulouz region was marginalised for many years. It was largely overlooked by the PMV³ agricultural actions and by the

1 “Per acampa li ouliva, li cau un fouol soubre et una sageta souta” (Raybaut, 1982, 509).

2 Vareo is a technique which consists in hitting the branches with a vareo stick, in order for the fruits to fall off.

3 Plan Maroc Vert, literally “Green Morocco Plan”, is a program launched in 2008 by the Moroccan Ministry of Agriculture for the development of a “modern and supportive agriculture”.

INDH⁴, but is now one of the targets of the new Génération Green⁵ plan. On the plain, the harvest of the olives represents a short period in the agricultural calendar – between the saffron season on the plateaus and the orange season in the neighbouring fields. The labour is not mechanised, and therefore requires a large workforce and employs most of the agricultural day labourers at this time of the year.

Staying with a family of olive farmers and taking part in the harvest allowed me to access various places where social and economic life is organised during the season. For this ethnography I worked with an interpreter, Fatima Boucheikha⁶, who accompanied me in the olive groves to conduct participant observation and during my conversations with the villagers. Thanks to her I was able to go from French, to Darija and Tachelhit⁷. This research constitutes the first fieldwork of my doctorate work in Anthropology, which I began at the end of 2019. I chose to go far from the intensive farming of the North of the country and from the big development projects, to go where the olive cultivation remains manual so I could start from the beginning of the process – that is, the day labourers' routine during a manual and food-producing harvest. I was able to conduct observations from the position of a worker by picking olives with the employees, but also because my friend Jamal and I held a field in usufruct. As it is also the case in the rest of the Mediterranean, many Moroccans resort to this kind of seasonal investment to harvest with their families or friends the olives they will sell or keep for their own use. As a foreigner and an academic researcher, I was able to enter places that are usually reserved to men (*cafes*, *meaşra*⁸) and to do what is considered to be male tasks (such as negotiating anything that has to do with a field or an olive press). However, as other female researchers have observed during their fieldwork – Blondet in 2008, Jeanjean in 2015 – being a woman made it difficult to have access to certain information, including when it came to the male workers or the men of the households.

4The Initiative Nationale pour le Développement Humain, literally “National Human Development Initiative”, was launched by King Mohammed IV of Morocco in 2005 and is managed by the Ministry of Home Affairs in order to prevent poverty, precariousness, and social exclusion.

5The “Green Generation” plan is an agricultural project with the ambition of an important irrigation project in the Sous region – the starting point being the Aoulouz dam.

6Fatima Boucheikha comes from the Sous region. She has a degree in Sociology from Agadir University and used to teach Philosophy in Aoulouz' secondary school. After having finished a Master's degree in Gender and Social Change in Paris University, she is now a journalist.

7Dajira is the Moroccan Arabic dialect. However, Tachelhit is the language that is the most used where this fieldwork takes place. It is an Amazigh (Berber) language from the South of the country. The words in italics and in brackets are the Tachelhit or Arabic transcriptions of the spoken words. Quotes in Tachelhit have been translated by Fatima Boucheikha and transcribed with the help of Ramdane Touati.

8‘Oil mill’. From the Arabic root ‘*aşara* (‘to crush’, ‘to press’). *Meaşir* is its plural form.

The olive harvest season⁹ shapes a unique and cyclical temporality and landscape. Both define, at the scale of the village and of the region, economic and social relationships, the assignments of status and social roles, and the distributions of the resources they underlie. Some people – such as Jmya, an olive farmer – believe in a purely meritorious distribution of the fruits, while others – like her sister-in-law – think that anyone should benefit from the harvest. One day she tells Jmya, in Tachelhit: ‘Some people work, some don’t, or they beg – so what? One shouldn’t speak ill of anyone – everyone has a right to their share of olives!’¹⁰ What share? Who can lay claim to it? Why? And at what cost? From the owners to those who transport the olives, the analysis of the scenes of harvest and of the adjoining activities provides some answers to these questions. In this article¹¹ I offer to follow the itinerary of the Aoulouz olives, which are first cultivated by those who own the trees, harvested by family or employed hands, then transported, shared, pressed and sold by others.

Finding One’s Place, Finding One’s Share: Agricultural Owners and Workers During the Harvest

It is early December, the temperatures drop, and snow occasionally covers the summits of the Atlas Mountains which overlook the Aoulouz plain. In the fields, women are already picking up the olives that have fallen too early. The owners keep an eye on their trees – as well as those of their neighbours – and on the weather, while organising their teams. The workers are waiting for the starting signal. As soon as the harvest begins, everyone will find their place – the owners and their wives, the seasonal workers, the employees from the village and the younger people. This first section of the article shows how the distribution is organised for those who join the harvest first. Although they all face specific difficulties, the barrier of access to the land and the principle of gendered complementarity of tasks tend to minimise the value of the women’s contribution and therefore the share they are entitled to.

Brahim is in his forties and owns several fields of olive trees in the South part of Aoulouz – near my host family’s home. It is by his side and with his team that I experience the olive harvest, and it is with him that I also experience being an usufructuary on one of his plots of land. Brahim has been living on the income of his olive oil for only a few years. He used

⁹The season during which olives are harvested.

¹⁰In Jmya’s field, on 5th December 2019.

¹¹The writing of this article was possible thanks to Didier Guignard and Béatrice Mesini’s kind and knowledgeable support.

to have to work in a slaughterhouse to make ends meet, in addition to his olive-growing work. Now that he has enough mature trees, cultivating olives meets his family's needs. He has placed a lot of hope in this year's harvest as, once the season is over, he will marry his daughter. During the harvest, the owner - *buzayt*¹² - goes back and forth between the field, the house and the mill. He looks after the land, the irrigation canals and the trees, he has to make sure the workers have all of the necessary equipment, and he sometimes participates in the *vareo* with the men.

This year the payment that the workers get from Brahim is lower than the agricultural minimum wage¹³. However, he has offered many times an advance to the women in case they can't afford to wait until the end of the harvest. For, even if the employees' financial precariousness limits any negotiation on their wages or working conditions, the owners do not feel particularly reassured. Those of them who turn to a workforce who is not family have to be certain of the workers' reliability and loyalty. Abdu, a small Aoulouz olive farmer, says:

It is difficult to find reliable people. One day they come, the next day they don't, you know it's not okay if you've booked your turn at the mill but then nobody turns up to pick the olives! This year I haven't found anyone - not even women - to pick [my olives]. With my brother and a friend we'll be doing all of the work - it will be very, very long¹⁴.

The same goes for Jmya, the only female landowner I've met in Aoulouz. She lives in a house near the olive groves with her three sisters - and no man. Neither of them is married and their brother lives in the house in front of theirs with his wife. Jmya owns various fields close to where she lives, in which she mainly cultivates olive trees but also fodder for the animals and a few vegetables and legumes. She also picks many edible or medicinal wild plants. She is proud of her job:

I work in agriculture (*tafellaht*), I'm happy. I do not want anything else than to work in agriculture, to take care of my land (*akal-inu*). Also, my mother is strong, she comes from Tata. She raised us all the same, boys and girls, that's why I know how to do everything in the fields¹⁵.

¹²Literally "he to whom the oil belongs".

¹³This year in Aoulouz the owners pay the men 120 Moroccan dirhams (DH) per day and the women 35DH (11,20 euros and 3,30 euros respectively). The agricultural minimum wage (SMAG) is 75DH per day.

¹⁴Abdu, in French, on 10th December 2019 over a meal in his home in Aoulouz.

¹⁵Jmya, in Tachelhit, on 16th December 2019 in her field in Aoulouz during the harvest.

**[Brahim with a vareo stick in his field
Aoulouz, November 2019 (© L. Florenza)]**

During the harvest season, Jmya picks olives each day in the fields with her sister Rana and two men she has been employing for the vareo for many years. Like the male owners, she has to make sure her employees are loyal. However, as a woman, she faces another kind of difficulty which concerns the inheritance of her land.

My brother doesn't want to work in the olive tree fields - he used to build houses. ... But there is nothing, no inheritance document (*iwriqen n waxan*) that says that I've left him my mother's house and that he leaves my father's fields to me. Even if everybody is happy like that, my sister-in-law isn't happy (*ur as-iejib lhal*). She wants more money [she clicks her tongue], so she says we have to do a proper heritage and share the fields with my brother¹⁶.

Jmya could lose a big part of her land if her brother, pressured by his wife, were to claim a share of the inheritance. According to the FAO [the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations], only one percent of the women in rural Morocco are landowners¹⁷. Thanks to the fight of the *sulaliyat*¹⁸ women, they now legally appear on the list of the parties entitled

¹⁶Jmya in Tachelhit, on 5th December 2019 in her home in Aoulouz over a cup of tea.

¹⁷A study by the FAO concerning the integration of gender in the agricultural and rural sectors, presented in Rabat on 6th March 2018.

¹⁸From the Arabic word *al-sulāla*, meaning 'extraction', 'ethnic lineage'. Used "to name a person who belongs to an ethnic community who owns common land, and whose members are related by a common genealogy" (Berriane & Rignall, 2017, 97).

to the succession of the collective lands. Concerning private land, the rules of inheritance are a complex mix of Muslim law (*šari'a*), customary law (*'urf*), and land law imposed under French colonialism (Berriane & Rignall, 2017). These different norms can indeed be restrictive, but, as Bina Agarwal has shown in the case of India, keeping women out of ownership and management of the land is also the result of exclusionary practices on a larger scale - including family pressures (Agarwal, 1988). Jmya's words express these prejudices: 'It's not fair (*iga dđulem*), I'm the one who cultivates the land (*ixeddamen n wakal*), I'm the one who needs it and my brother doesn't care!'¹⁹

Concerning seasonal workers, family norms and pressure also exert influence on the way they find their place. For women, the principle of gendered division of work strongly determines the tasks and the benefits they can lay claim to. Like in other Mediterranean areas, small olive farm management is a family matter, and harvest season is often a moment of reunion in which members of the extended family participate (Raybaut, 1982). However, for owners like Brahim, Abdu, or Jmya who do not have family help, seasonal workers are necessary. These men and women can be seen every morning and evening in small groups, walking or in the back of a pickup truck, on the tracks and roads leading to the olive tree fields. Brahim's team is composed of nine people: four men and five women. The latter often say that in wintertime, they would rather wait for the orange harvest, which pays better money (80 dirhams per day) and for which they don't have to spend the entire day in a squatting position. During the orange harvest women are close to men, especially during the journeys in the back of the pickup and in the tree rows. For this reason their fathers, brothers or husbands sometimes dissuade or prohibit them from taking the job. Fatima tells me:

One day mum said to my father: 'I think I will go and work in the orange fields.' He made a face and told her: 'Do you really need anything, honestly? There's meat in the fridge!' It's really frowned upon, you see.²⁰

Unlike the orange harvest, the olive harvest is organised into simultaneous and complementary tasks between men and women. This implies a strict spatial distribution, as well as a division of the different tasks and tools - which are distributed depending on the gender of the employees. The vareo stick (*amzwaye*), is a good illustration of this. Carved in flexible wood, it has been used since Antiquity to harvest olives. With a hard blow (*ssus*) the men hit the tip of the branches so the olives fall to the ground, where a canvas has been spread out beforehand. When a tree is emptied of its fruit, the men grab the corners of the canvas to gather the

¹⁹Jmya, in Tachelhit, on 5th December 2019 in her home in Aoulouz over a cup of tea.

²⁰Fatima, in French, on 2nd December 2019 in her flat in Aoulouz.

olives, the branches and the fallen leaves. "It's the men's task. The height of the trees and the width of the foliage require strength, skill, balance, and [to take] risks" (Raybaut, 1982, 509). This job is considered to be difficult and tiring, which justifies the exclusion of women from it and the men's higher wage - in this case, almost four times higher. According to Paola Tabet, it is not the biological causes but rather the differentiated usage of the tools that constitutes the fundamental factor of the sexual division of labour. Therefore, there are not strictly speaking female tasks - merely 'residual' tasks. They do not require the addition of complex tools - this would lead to their masculinisation (Tabet, 1998).

Here, the 'residual' activity is undoubtedly picking the olives from the ground. The women's work consists in squatting around the trees which have just been beaten by the men. They manually pick up the fruit fallen outside of the canvas from the ground (*gerrunt*) - oftentimes wearing gloves - by seizing them in between their thumb and index. Considered to be less strong but quicker and 'more gentle' than men, they move around crouching, rapidly fill up both hands with olives and throw them with precision into the basket (Hellio, 2008 ; Moreno-Nieto, 2012 ; Bossenbroek, 2016). Selection (*yarbal*) is done with the foliage remover (*buseyyar*), one of the rare tools used by the women. Once the men have brought the canvas in the middle of the field, the women sit in a circle around it, bring part of the pile close to them and get rid of the branches. Then one of them fills a basket with olives and empties it on the foliage remover made of a tilted grid on which the olives roll until they fall into a big tray, rid of their leaves. Once the tray is full of the leafless olives, two or three people empty it in a big canvas sack.

It seems that when there are fewer women in the team or when the pace is slower, the men can momentarily stop the vareo in order to take care of the selection of the olives, but they never perform tasks on the ground. Conversely, I have never seen a woman take care of the vareo. Keltoum is surprised when I show her pictures of women equipped with long electric rakes, harvesting without men in the Moroccan Rif region: 'Oh no, it's too difficult (*iceqqa bahra*), us women can't do that. It is not possible (*ur ittimken*), this doesn't take place in Morocco! I wouldn't be able to do this anyway.'²¹ Yet, many studies insist precisely on the physical arduousness of the agricultural jobs usually allotted to women, and Bina Agarwal - as well as Paola Tabet - shows that this distribution is the result of the male appropriation of technology more than a biological explanation. I believe that her analysis of the taboos concerning the cart "forbidding women from ploughing, which seem to be widespread in most cultures" (Agarwal, 1988, 562) could also apply to the vareo stick, rarely seen in a woman's hands. This established fact has existed since Antiquity on both

²¹Keltoum, in Tachelhit, on 20th December 2019 over lunch in her home in Aoulouz.

sides of the Mediterranean, and it is still the case today, as the Spanish workers' recent demands show. These women are more and more supplanted from the harvesting teams, replaced by machines and by men – who are the only ones trained to use them (Anta Félez & Peinado Rodríguez, 2019).

The owners of the fields, therefore, have access to an important part of the olives in this economy. This is because they possess landed property, because they have their family members' free labour at their disposal, and because they are financially able to employ other people. Nevertheless, the owners' situations are fragile, as they depend on the vagaries of the weather, on their employees' loyalty and on the price of olive oil. My conversations with Jmya bring to light the juridical, social, and cultural mechanisms which are at the origin of a strong inequality – based on gender – when it comes to the access to the resources of the land. However, her story also shows that it is possible for a woman to have access to the results of her own harvest. For the employees I met, their share of the harvest is materialised by a meagre wage accorded to them only after a field's harvest is completed. With the support of essentializing arguments, the less well paid tasks, those that are regarded as straightforward or residual, are left for the women to do.

Sharing, Pressing, Transporting: Beyond the Harvest

January is near, the fields are crowded, and everywhere around the village olives come pouring down like rain. The fruits pile up in bags; donkeys pull carts overloaded with olives on every track that leads towards tarred roads in order to unload them into piles in the courtyards of the *mēaşir*. Once the fruits are plucked from the trees, other helping hands participate in this economy. It is the gleaners', millers', and carriers' turn to join in and to get their share of the harvest.

Almost every day I see a small group of children or women in the field who shyly come forward with plastic bags. When seeing them, the owner grabs a basket filled with olives by the workers and pours a certain amount into their bags. The group of people then repeats a religious phrase while thanking and blessing the owner and their family. I witness daily, in the fields and in the homes, debates concerning these women called *imeg°ran*²². They are a target for various rumours and are either considered to be legitimate enough – because they are poor, isolated, incapable of

²²From the Berber root *MGR*, 'to harvest'. *Img°ri*, and its plural form *imeg°ran*, means "those who harvest"; here the meaning is closer to the word 'gleaners'.

working, honest, pious – or not legitimate enough to ask for and receive olives. One day, while harvesting, Karima and Farida debate on the subject:

Karima: It is normal (*ur g-is walu*), it is not a bad thing (*kra ixcenn*) because she is not committing a crime, and she is not stealing. So it is her right (*dar-s lhaq*).

Farida: No, it is not proper behaviour because she can work, make an effort and not ask for olives that are already harvested like she does. Especially because she sells them afterwards and that's not right (*ur iga eadi*).²³

[Mohamed empties the sacks of olives and prepares them for the first stage of extraction

Aoulouz, December 2019 (© L. Florenza)]

This donation relies on the importance of sharing with those in need, one of the five pillars of Islam. With the *ṣadaqa* ('charity'), the owners are giving to others. Fatima explains: 'When you have something, you have to give to the poor, it is for *baraka*. Because what you give in olives to the *imeg°ran*, God will double it.'²⁴ The presence of these women enables – through the act of giving – a kind of social and religious redistribution of the olives as a resource. For small owners like Jmya, however, it is a financially heavy load in the event of a bad harvest, and it is socially uncomfortable because she is on poor terms with some of these women. It can sometimes also come across as unfair towards the workers. The olives or, indeed, the oil that these people ask for – sometimes even in the mill –

²³Karima and Farida, in Tachelhit, on 17th December 2019 in Brahim's field in Aoulouz, during harvest.

²⁴Fatima, on 3rd December 2019 over a meal in her flat in Aoulouz.

are seemingly often sold straight away and not used for their personal consumption. The fruits are thus brought out of the gift network and enter in marketed exchanges to which the workers have no access. A relatively important quantity of the harvest is therefore given to these women, whether for it to end up in their homes or for it to be resold to sellers or *mēašir*.

The owners and employees of the *mēašir* are other key auxiliaries of the harvest, because it is thanks to them that the olives are transformed into oil. There are many hundreds of *mēašir* in the Aoulouz region. There are two types of units: the traditional ones, where the millstone is pulled by a horse and the press is operated by two men, and the semimodern units which run on electricity. Each technique comes with its cost and its taste, and the owners chose according to different criteria which are part of “a food culture where olive oil appears to be a strong indicator of a sense of belonging” (Aumeeruddy-Thomas & Caubet, 2017). For instance, my host family possess their own semimodern *mēašir*, managed by Mustafa who is the head of the household. Abdu, however, always goes to the small village mill because he likes the strong taste which results from a traditional grinding. Brahim brings his olives to a friend of the family, and Jamal and I bring ours to a friend of his, Mohamed, who has just built a mechanical mill.

The millers I met in Aoulouz estimate the total weight of the harvest, from which they deduct a certain percentage by way of payment, in the form of olive oil, for the press service. The presses are an exclusively masculine space. There are no women because it is a place said to be dirty: the olives are left in the sun and emit a strong smell, and the employees are constantly covered in oil. It is also a place of physical and technical movements which are inaccessible to them: the engines have to be started and the pressure has to be controlled, the fruits have to be carried to the millstone and unloaded, and physical strength can be necessary to activate the manual press. Just like in the fields, the distribution of the working space and of the different tasks is also a result of the appropriation of the technique by the men, and of gender stereotypes – to which it contributes.

Other more or less visible actors participate in the harvest economy. When the olives are almost ripe, rumours concerning ‘the thieves’ (*imexxaren*) immediately start to spread, so much so that some men become ‘guards’ (*andafen*) of the fields. Jmya often warns us against the thieves who supposedly come to our field during the night. That is how one morning, while harvesting for the first time the plot we have rented, we meet three men who introduce themselves as those who have been protecting our olives until our arrival. On Brahim's advice – and despite our scepticism about the authenticity of their work – we pay them. At this time of the year work in the fields is difficult and intense, so musicians go from

parcel to parcel in order to entertain the gatherers in exchange for money. They wear traditional garments and are either a single man or a small group of three or four men. They sing to the beat of their *guembris*²⁵ and drums and everybody dances, sings, and claps as they go past. Lastly, those who drive delivery tricycles, vans and buses form a network of men who are sought to transport either the olives or the oil. The owners who lack the means to transport their harvest turn to them to bring their olives to the *mēaṣir*. They can also ask for the drivers to deliver the oil to buyers from other villages - or even as far as Agadir or Ouarzazate - in exchange for money, services or olive oil. The majority of these people occupy the 'odd jobs' of an informal sector which represents 80% of Morocco's employment (World Bank and Morocco's Higher Planning Commission, 2016).

These men and women, therefore, directly participate in the production or in the spirit of this collective moment that is the harvest. The 'residual' tasks which do not require specific tools or skills are the only ones accessible to women. Moreover, there is a difference in the very nature of the profit which results from the harvest's subsidiary tasks. The activities that are open to women offer a remuneration in kind (unprocessed olives), whereas those that are open to men offer - most of the time - a financial payment. To come full circle, it is important to note that the different marketing stages are taken care of by the men, for they consist in spending time in public spaces that are hardly open to women - such as town squares, bus stations, markets and cafes.

The Foot Soldiers of the Harvest: Women in the Homes, Women in the Fields

Harvesting season is in full swing. There are more bare trees every day, the *mēaṣir* run at full capacity and the cans of oil are starting to overrun the stalls of the markets. All of the protagonists I've mentioned continue their daily work with the trees, the fields and the mills. Yet, this wouldn't last long if there weren't an army of busy hands to bustle about behind the scenes - or rather, behind the walls of the homes. According to Bina Arwa, analysing a traditional agricultural activity by restricting oneself to public spaces and to those of the formal work amounts to considering the owners' and workers' households to be mere monolithic units of analysis, while "ignor[ing] the inter-domestic gendered dimensions" (Agarwal, 1988, 531). If one opens their front doors, however, one discovers the existence of many productive activities which, directly or indirectly, participate in the harvest - and through which the women and the girls attempt in various

²⁵A plucked instrument of the Gnaoua people.

ways to reclaim their share.

In my host family, Lala Rqayya, the grandmother, is head of a large household which includes her three sons, their wives, and children. The men are very often outside, so the house is mainly occupied by the daughters-in-law, the granddaughters, and the young grandsons. Most of the domestic life takes place in the kitchen and in the adjoining room where there is a bread oven. A small Moroccan sitting room serves as a dining room for the women and the children, and it is also where we gather to eat and drink tea. The domestic chores are organised according to a strict schedule. Every day one of the daughters-in-law or granddaughters is responsible for a specific chore such as making bread, cooking the meals, cleaning the floor, doing the laundry - in addition to the children's upbringing and the cleaning of the bedrooms. In their neighbour's home, Jmya is the one who acts as the 'head of the household' (*lytucka*) for her sisters. With her sister Rana, she takes care of the harvest of the olives, works the land and takes care of the irrigation. As for Khadija and Khadra, they take care of the domestic chores and the animals. It is interesting to note that, in the absence of men, a certain distribution of the chores occurs between the 'inside' women and the 'outside' women. Jmya and Rana undertake the jobs that are traditionally masculine, and their sisters carry out those that are traditionally feminine.

**[Karima's hands, while she rids the olives of their leaves and branches
Aoulouz, December 2019 (© L. Florenza)]**

In the households, all of the women's domestic chores increase during the olive harvest because the daily rhythm of work intensifies. For instance, the task of cooking lunch falls on the olive groves owners' wives. Every day, I see them on their way to the fields, with tagine pots on their heads. They feed the men of their family and the workers. This, however, is not considered to be a job which participates in the economy of the harvest, but rather like a domestic chore like any other. The women's political and

economic advances, especially since the 2004 *Mudawana* reform²⁶, and their participation in the households' incomes are not accompanied by a more equitable distribution of the domestic duties. Work that is carried out at home is regarded as non-work, and women's financial contributions as mere complementary salaries²⁷. This view of the family roles can explain why some tasks such as cooking and bringing food to the workers do not entitle the owner's wife to claim for an individual share from the harvest of the olives.

Beyond the question of gender, age is also a determining criterion when it comes to accessing the fruits of the harvest. Even though their living conditions are better and the work is less difficult than those of the previous generations, opportunities for a future for the youth of rural areas remain limited. All of the young women I met in Aoulouz told me that they did not want to work in the olive growing sector. Young people have little chance to profit from this activity, for they often have to contribute for free to the effort of the harvest as family helpers²⁸, or to take a job in another family in exchange for a low income. Although the government has included new subsidies²⁹ to help young agricultural entrepreneurs start their own businesses and acquire equipment - which could be a source of hope for those who wish to stay in their village - the anthropologist Lisa Bossenbroeck shows that these opportunities are highly gendered (Bossenbroeck *et al.*, 2015). In her study only young men and not women expressed a desire to have an agricultural activity, and the young men were also the main recipients and targets of the government subsidies. Amongst the young women's projects, that of becoming a housewife prevails - it is the case for Keltoum, Brahim's employee. In second place comes the desire to turn domestic activities into activities which generate income - such as Ghizlane's *randa*³⁰.

Ghizlane is one of Lala Rqayya's granddaughters. She is twenty-one years old and has recently returned to her family home after having dropped out of her first year at the university of Agadir. Aside from doing domestic chores, she spends most of her time on her smartphone talking to her sisters who live in the city or in Europe. She also watches a lot of videos and goes on websites specialised in *randa*, because she would like to make it her job. Her sister-in-law Zayna, who is twenty-four, is the last to have joined the family. Like Ghizlane, she spends about half an hour every day picking up olives in the fields close to the house. One day, after having

26Moroccan Code of Personal Status that governs family law.

27The contribution to the household's financial resources is written in the *Mūdawana* (art. 194) as an obligation only for the man.

28In Morocco, almost 2 million people - often women and young people - work for a family member without any compensation, in the agricultural sector or the craft industry, and are not counted in the working population (Puchot, 2020).

29*Génération Green* 2020-2030.

30Fine hand embroidery which is used as an ornament for kaftans.

accompanied them, I write down while relistening to the recording:

They take a plastic bucket and walk slowly, bending down to pick up the windfalls that are too ripe or that have been nibbled. As I help her fill up her bucket, I ask Zayna why she's picking up olives. She looks at me with surprise: 'I'm not picking up olives!' She blushes and laughs nervously, then says: 'No, I don't do that. I'm not picking up olives, it's ... [she hesitates] the other women who do that.' I ask her if it's for cooking. 'No, it's not for cooking, there are people who come, who buy the olives.' She fills about half of the bucket, then goes inside and leaves it in a cupboard. She will come back to fetch it the following day until it's full, then sellers will come by the house and buy it from her (30 dirhams). 'With the money I buy clothes for Mohammed, I save up and buy myself presents, like jewellery.' When I ask the same question to Ghizlane, she tells me: 'I buy mobile phone top-up cards for the Internet and fabric for the *randa*.' (Extracts from the fieldwork report of 27th November 2019).

This exchange with Zayna shows how women negotiate their identity every day at the junction of their statuses and roles as housewives, daughters, mothers, and employees. The confusion she felt during our conversation reveals perhaps an "identity blurring" which is defined by Leïla Bouasria as being "the gap between what is desired and reality" (Bouasria, 2016, 239). That is to say a gap she might feel between her wish to correspond to the image of the housewife kept by her husband and her need to complement the couple's income - while, at the same time, differentiating herself from the employees. The employees attempt to fill this gap in different ways with strategies of "dissimulation and attachment" of feminine and masculine identities attributes to which individuals have to conform to in the eyes of society (Bouasria, 2016, 239).

When it comes to female workers, these strategies are more difficult to put into place because, as opposed to the owners' wives like Zayna or Ghizlane, they are often their family's main source of income. As the dialogue becomes more natural in spite of my presence, I realise that for these women harvesting olives is not simply a "small temporary job" (*tamuqeft*³¹), as they present it. Added to the rest of the agricultural activities they do all year round, it is in actual fact the basis of their families' subsistence. In Brahim's team, two of the women are married to very ill men, one is an isolated widow. As for Keltoum, she provides her parents' main income. For financial reasons, they are therefore forced to distance themselves from the ideal image of the housewife.

However - just like the female workers employed by the *muqef*³² who Lisa

³¹From the word *muqef*, which is generally used to describe a seasonal job.

Bossenbroeck studied – they can reduce the gap and come closer to their identity as housewives by recreating some sort of family space within the public space of the agricultural work. Keltoum expresses this in the following way:

Despite the fact that it is hard work (*tammara*), we thank God for everything. Things go smoothly (*lehna*), especially when I work with people from my family or my neighbours. I always prefer to work with people I know (*ayt leblad*), so that there are no problems (*Imacakil*)³³.

By working with their family or with female friends, they ensure an inner protection and social control. Here, it is materialised by constant calls to order concerning the rules of modesty (wearing clothes that cover the body properly, not addressing men directly or working too close to them, etc.). Karima is the eldest of the team and severely points out a headscarf that is sliding off or laughter that is too loud. Moreover, by choosing employers and workplaces close to their homes they avoid the dangers and gossip that affect the women who move about on their own or in pickups, because they walk together and work for someone related to their family circle. This kind of “extension of the domestic space to the field” (Bossenbroeck, 2019, 105) allows them to negotiate the identity blurring mentioned previously. By their actions and discourse, they disguise the family configuration of a household in which the wife is entirely or mainly at the origin of the resources and which is considered “unconventional” – thus undermining “the male identity edifice”, which can be a source of conflict in the private sphere and of dishonour in the public sphere (Bouasria, 2016, 240).

Another way of accessing the profits of the harvest is to participate in what Meriem Rodary calls “the women’s commerce” (Rodary, 2007, 772). This economic sphere is constituted by informal female activities, which enable them to have a certain control of the profits of the production. However necessary it is to open up access to the formal economic sphere for women, Meriem Rodary warns us against the destruction of this informal economic sphere that allows women to “preserve an invisibility from which they benefit a certain freedom” (Rodary, 2007, 782). Zayna and Ghizlane picking and selling olives from their garden, almost secretly, is an example of that same commerce. In her study of the Rif region, Kenza Afsahi notes a comparable practice: a young girl confesses regularly and secretly taking almonds to sell them, in order to earn money which she then spends on entertainment (Afsahi, 2015). Secretly keeping part of one’s earnings, bartering, or selling part of one’s domestic production are also examples given by Meriem Rodary and Bina Agarwal. For example, on one occasion while we are at Jmya’s place, some young people from one of the village associations pass by ‘to make the women work (*ad ssexdamen*) and

³³Keltoum, in Tachelhit, on the phone via Fatima on 10th May 2020.

to sell their production in order to help them'³⁴. Jmya then offers to make some bread and to sell it to them. Whereas the owners' wives and the *imeg°ran* can resort to almost all of these strategies, the female employees' margin of action, on the other hand, is often limited to hiding part of their income. Their husbands then more or less pretend to be unaware of these savings whose purposes, according to the women, they would disapprove of - including contributions to wedding ceremonies.

Conclusion

This study shows how, at the scale of a village and during the unique period that is harvest, the economic and social benefits of olive cultivation are negotiated and shared amongst those who turn the fruits into oil. Similarly to the khat, studied by Céline Lesourd, these fruits distribute the benefits and "there's something in it for everybody. ... social peace is somewhat achieved, 'because we live thanks to the tree. All of us.'" (Lesourd, 2019, 20). Owners, housewives, workers, millers or guards - each, more or less visibly and in their own way, take part in the harvest and get distinct benefits out of the olive trees. For "although every forager dances ... not all the dances are alike. Each dance is shaped by communal histories ... " (Tsing, 2015, 241). These dances, being impregnated by male appropriation of the resources and techniques, condition the unequal distribution of the production to which each and everyone can lay claim. At the heart of these disparities, I have attempted in this article to understand the gender dynamics which are at stake in the distribution of the land, of the tasks and of the benefits of the harvest. It is also an attempt to - indirectly - understand the individuals' relationship to the different roles they occupy.

On one hand, this study provides an insight on how gender is an essential criterion to understanding the unequal distribution of labour and the access to the resources in rural Morocco - as well as in other so-called developed countries, or not. It is at the intersection with other factors such as age, social or marital status, profession or reputation that the share obtained by the different actors during the olive harvest is defined. On the other hand this analysis shows that however reduced women's share is compared to those of men, it is neither because they do not take part in the harvest's economy, nor because of biological reasons. The main reason is that their access to the resources is limited by numerous legal, economic, cultural, political, and religious barriers. Because "Moroccan women were never prevented from working, rather it is their access to the benefits generated by their labour which the social order tries to limitate - whatever

34A member of the association explains in Tachelhit to Fatima what they do, at Jmya's place, on 5th December 2019.

the period under study” (Rodary, 2007, 757).

Bibliography

Afsahi, Kenza. 2015. « Pas de culture de cannabis sans les femmes. Le cas du Rif au Maroc ». *Deviance et Societe* Vol. 39 (1): 73-97.

Agarwal, Bina. 1988. « Who Sows? Who Reaps? Women and Land Rights in India ». *The Journal of Peasant Studies* 15 (4): 531-81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03066158808438377>.

———. 1994. « Gender, Resistance and Land: Interlinked Struggles over Resources and Meanings in South Asia ». *Journal of Peasant Studies* 22 (1): 81-125. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03066159408438567>.

Anta Félez, José-Luis, et Matilde Peinado Rodríguez. 2019. « Las mujeres en el olivar andaluz. Nuevas y viejas formas en el trabajo agrícola ». *methaodos revista de ciencias sociales* 7 (2): 302-13. <https://doi.org/10.17502/m.rcs.v7i2.285>.

Aumeeruddy-Thomas, Yildiz, et Dominique Caubet. 2017. « Savoirs paysans autour des huiles d’olive. Rif, nord du Maroc ». *Revue d’ethnoécologie*, n° Supplément 1.

Banque Mondiale et Haut-Commissariat au Plan. 2016. *Le marché du travail au Maroc : défis et opportunités*. URL : <https://www.banquemondiale.org/fr/country/morocco/publication/lab-or-market-in-morocco-challenges-and-opportunities>

Berriane, Yasmine, et Karen Rignall. 2017. « La fabrique de la coutume au Maroc : le droit des femmes aux terres collectives ». *Cahiers du Genre* n° 62 (1): 97-118.

Blondet, Marieke. 2008. *Le genre de l’anthropologie. Faire du terrain au féminin* In *Les politiques de l’enquête*. La Découverte.

Bossenbroek, Lisa. 2016. « Les nouvelles modalités du travail agricole dans le Saïss au Maroc : l’émergence des inégalités identitaires entre l’ouvrier et l’ouvrière ? » In *Le Maroc au présent : D’une époque à l’autre, une société en mutation*, édité par Assia Boutaleb et et al., 365-74. Description du Maghreb. Maroc: Centre Jacques-Berque. <http://books.openedition.org/cjb/1054>.

———. 2019. « Les ouvrières agricoles dans le Saïss au Maroc, actrices de changements sociaux ? » *Alternatives Rurales*, n° 7 (décembre): 15.

Bossenbroek, Lisa, Jan Douwe van der Ploeg, et Margreet Zwarteveen. 2015. « Rêves brisés? Les jeunes et les changements agraires dans la région du Saïss au Maroc ». *Cahiers Agricultures* 24 (6): 342-48.

Bouasria, Leïla. 2016. « Les ouvrières chefs de foyer : entre “la modernité” du réel et le souhaitable “traditionnel” ». In *Le Maroc au présent : D’une époque à l’autre, une société en mutation*, édité par

Assia Boutaleb et et al., 327-34. Description du Maghreb. Maroc: Centre Jacques-Berque. <http://books.openedition.org/cjb/1044>.

Hellio, Emmanuelle. 2008. « Importer des femmes pour exporter des fraises (Huelva) ». *Études rurales*, n° 182 (juillet): 185-200. <https://doi.org/10.4000/etudesrurales.8867>.

Jeanjean, Agnès. 2015. « Une ethnologue, des égoutiers et des universitaires. Rapports sexués, rapports politiques ». In *Le sexe de l'enquête: Approches sociologiques et anthropologiques*, édité par Anne Monjaret et Catherine Pugeault. Sociétés, Espaces, Temps. Lyon: ENS Éditions. <http://books.openedition.org/enseditions/3981>.

Lesourd, Céline. 2019. *Puissance khat: La vie politique d'une plante stimulante*. Presses Universitaires de France - PUF.

Mathieu, Nicole-Claude. 2004. « Entrée « Sexe et genre » ». In *Dictionnaire critique du féminisme*, 2e éd. augm. Paris: Presses Universitaires de France - PUF.

Moreno-Nieto, Juana. 2012. « "Faut-Il Des Mains de Femmes Pour Cueillir Les Fraises ? » Dynamique de La Gestion de La Main-d'œuvre et Du Travail Dans Le Secteur Fraisier Du Périmètre Irrigué Du Loukkos (Maroc) ». *Études et Essais Du Centre Jacques Berque*, n° 11.

Puchot, Pierre. 2020. « Au Maroc, « on te traite comme un insecte » ». *Le Monde diplomatique*, 1 avril 2020. <https://www.monde-diplomatique.fr/2020/04/PUCHOT/61613>.

Raybaut, Paul. 1982. « La récolte des olives en Provence Orientale ». *Le Monde alpin et rhodanien. Revue régionale d'ethnologie* 10 (1): 505-17. <https://doi.org/10.3406/mar.1982.1185>.

Rodary, Meriem. 2007. « Le travail des femmes dans le Maroc précolonial, entre oppression et résistance: Droit au travail ou accès aux bénéfices ? » *Cahiers d'études africaines* 47 (187-188): 753-80. <https://doi.org/10.4000/etudesafriaines.9082>.

Scott, Joan. 1988. « Genre: Une catégorie utile d'analyse historique - Persée ». *Les Cahiers du GRIF* Le genre de l'histoire: 125-53. [French traduction of :Scott, Joan. 1986. « Gender: A Useful Category of Historical Analysis ». *The American Historical Review*, Vol. 91: 1053-1075.]

Tabet, Paola. 1998. *La Construction Sociale de l'inégalité des Sexes*. Éditions L'Harmattan.

Tsing, Anna Lowenhaupt. 2017. *Le champignon de la fin du monde: sur la possibilité de vivre dans les ruines du capitalisme*. [French traduction of : Tsing, Anna Lowenhaupt. 2015. *The Mushroom at the End of the World: On the Possibility of Life in Capitalist Ruins*, Princeton University Press.]